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АНАЛИЗ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ МОДЕЛИ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ ВУЗОВ В ЛАТВИИ

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ANALYSIS OF FEATURES OF THE MODEL OF STATE FUNDING OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN LATVIA

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Аннотация

Вопрос исследования опыта финансирования учреждений высшего образования стран Европы актуален особенно в условиях восстановления и реновации системы образования после победы. Снижение финансирования высшего образования, повышение требований к эффективности работы высшего образования предполагает поиск новых путей финансирования и использования положительного опыта стран, имеющих опыт решения подобных проблем. Целью данной статьи было создание рекомендаций по использованию опыта финансирования учреждений высшего образования Латвии в Украине. Для достижения цели исследования были использованы научные методы обобщения, классификации, дедукции и анализа. В исследовании очерчена общая проблематика финансирования учреждений высшего образования Латвии, законодательные акты и пути решения проблем финансирования высшего образования. Определены основные проблемы, с которыми сталкивались учреждения высшего образования разной формы собственности Латвии и сделаны выводы об эффективности разработанных государством шагов по улучшению финансирования высшего образования. Проанализированы основные подходы к государственному финансированию высшего образования, определены возможные пути внедрения опыта Латвии в Украинские заведения высшего образования. Практическим результатом работы является внедрение опыта Латвийских учреждений высшего образования в высшее образование Украины.

Abstract

The question of researching the experience of financing higher education institutions in European countries is relevant, especially in the conditions of restoration and renovation of the education system after the victory. Lowering the financing of higher education, increasing the requirements for the efficiency of higher education institutions requires the search for new ways of financing and using the positive experience of countries that have experience in solving similar problems. The purpose of this article was to create recommendations for using the experience of financing Latvian higher education institutions in Ukraine. To achieve the goal of the research, scientific methods of generalization, classification, deduction and analysis were used. A problem solving tree was created, the final goal of overcoming which is the development of recommendations. The study outlines the general problems of financing higher education institutions in Latvia, legislative acts and ways to solve the problems of financing higher education. The main problems faced by higher education institutions of different forms of ownership in Latvia were identified, and conclusions were drawn about the effectiveness of steps developed by the state to improve the financing of higher education. The main approaches to state funding of higher education institutions were analyzed, and possible ways of introducing Latvia's experience into Ukrainian higher education institutions were determined. The practical result of the work is the possibility of introducing the experience of Latvian institutions of higher education into the higher education of Ukraine.

Ключевые слова: высшее образование, финансирование, государство, высшее образование, модель.

Keywords: higher education, financing, state, higher education institution, model.

Turning to Latvia's experience in the field of financing higher education and financial autonomy of universities is explained by the following factors. First, in 2009, amendments were made to the "Law On Institutions of Higher Education 1995" [1], which provided

for a change in the legal status of higher education institutions from "budgetary institutions" on "derived public persons". The result of such a change was an increase in the level of financial autonomy of higher ed-

education institutions. Secondly, in 2015, a three-dimensional model of state financing of higher education institutions was introduced at the national level, containing the following components:

- "base funding" (basic financing of educational activities),
- "performance-based funding" (result-oriented funding),
- "development funding" (financing of the development of higher education and research).

Thirdly, the share of spending on higher education is 1.5% of GDP (1.2% - from state sources, 0.3% - from private sources) [2, c. 266-267], is equal to the value of OECD countries (1.54% of GDP) and exceeds the average value of EU countries (1.35% of GDP) [2, c. 261, 273].

The basic indicators characterizing higher education in Latvia are as follows:

- spending on higher education (according to purchasing power parity) – 23 million euros [3];
- spending on higher education – 1.5% of GDP [2, c. 266], of which 1.2% of GDP comes from state sources [2, c. 267, 273];
- expenses for 1 student (according to purchasing power parity) [4, c. 264] – 7448.6 dollars. USA;
- number of students per teacher (student-teacher ratio) – 17 [5; 6];
- the level of financial autonomy of universities is 89% [7].

The following types of higher education institutions are distinguished in Latvia [8; 9]:

- "university-type" offering academic and professional training programs;
- "non-university-type" offering professional training programs;
- *kolejja* (college) (provides higher professional education of the first level), can function as a structural division of a higher education institution, and as an independent institution.

Regulatory and legal support in the field of higher education includes the following key documents:

- "Law On Institutions of Higher Education 1995" [1] (Law "On Institutions of Higher Education") of 1995;
- "Cabinet Regulation No. 740 of 24 August 2004. Regulations Regarding Stipends, and other legal acts governing the financing of the sector" [10] (Cabinet Regulation "On Granting Stipends") of 2004;
- "Law on Budget and Financial Management 1994" [11] (Law "On Budget and Financial Management") of 1994;
- "Cabinet Regulation No. 994 of 12 December 2006. Procedures for the Financing of Institutions of Higher Education and Colleges from the Funds of the State Budget" [12] (Procedure for financing institutions of higher education and colleges from the State Budget);
- "Cabinet Regulation No. 1316 of 12 November 2013. Procedures for the Allocation of Financial Reference Amount to State Scientific Institutions, State Institutions of Higher Education and the Scientific Institutes of State Institutions of Higher Education" [13]

scientific institutes, state institutions of higher education, scientific institutes of state institutions of higher education);

- Ministru Kabinets rīkojums № 333 «Par jauna augstākās izglītības finansēšanas modeļa ieviešanu Latvijā» [14] (Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers "On the Introduction of a New Model of Funding for Higher Education in Latvia"), 2015.

The Ministry of Education and Science [15], the Parliament (Sejm) and the Cabinet of Ministers are responsible for the implementation of state policy in the field of higher education in Latvia at the national level. The interests of higher education institutions are represented in the Diet and the Cabinet of Ministers by the Minister of Education and Science. The Council of Higher Education [16] is an expert body on the development of higher education.

State funding of higher education institutions: national level According to Art. 78 "Law On Institutions of Higher Education 1995" [1] (Law "On Institutions of Higher Education") of 1995, public institutions of higher education in Latvia receive funding from the following sources [1]:

- the state budget for education in accordance with the optimal list of educational programs and the number of students. Such financing is aimed at covering the costs of utility payments, taxes, infrastructure maintenance, inventory and equipment acquisition, research work, staff wages;
- payment of education covered by the state or provided in the form of loans subject to or not subject to return;
- from the financial resources of the target purpose.

Public institutions of higher education in Latvia may receive additional funding from other sources of research funding. In clause 4 of Art. 78 "Law On Institutions of Higher Education 1995" [1] (Law "On Institutions of Higher Education") of 1995 also states that the Ministry of Education and Science [15] (Ministry of Education and Science), other ministries and state structures of Latvia may enter into agreements with self-governing bodies created by the state and other legal entities and individuals, institutions of higher education on the training of certain specialists or conducting research with the provision of appropriate state funding [1].

Any state structure or self-governing and private structure can independently conclude contracts with institutions of higher education on the training of certain specialists or conducting research with payment from the funds at their disposal, if this does not contradict the current legislative acts [1].

As taxpayers, higher education institutions in Latvia are equal to non-profit organizations and have the right to receive tax benefits in accordance with current legislation. Institutions are exempt from customs duties and fees, as well as from taxes for the import of materials and equipment for reconstruction (clause 5 of article 78 "Law On Institutions of Higher Education 1995" [1]). According to Clause 7 of Art. 78 "Law On Institutions of Higher Education 1995" [1] after submission of the annual state budget draft to the Seimas, the Cabinet

completed research projects and number of publications).

As part of the second component of "performance-based funding", World Bank experts proposed the following performance indicators for providing funding [20]:

- share of graduates, length of study, employment of graduates;
- number of students who obtained master's and doctor's degrees;
- the number of students who participated in international mobility, as well as invited teachers, international projects on research and educational cooperation;
- bibliometric indicators;
- the share of students participating in fundamental and applied research;
- research funding from external sources.

The third component "development funding" involves financing through the EU Structural Funds and the Government of Latvia, which finances strategic projects within the framework of various programs, such as Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, STEM (programs in the field of science, technology, engineering and mathematics) [20]. The new funding model keeps the indicator of the number of educational places as a basis, supplementing it with funding for the performance of higher education institutions, development and competition for the best results in teaching and research. Such a model links education and research funding, providing opportunities for higher education institutions to implement their tasks. Institutions of higher education receive a budget subsidy for training and research activities within the framework of a single amount of allocation, the structure and use of which is provided for in the agreement on the results of activity for a period of 3-5 years. Such an agreement includes requirements for reporting on the results achieved, which meet the conditions of the allocation of financial resources [20].

In accordance with the Regulation of the Cabinet of Ministers of Latvia "Par jauna augstākās izglītības finansēšanas modeļa ieviešanu Latvijā" [20] (On the introduction of a new model of funding for higher education in Latvia) of 2015, the principles of the distribution of the volume of funding according to the new funding model were defined, which provide for calculation based on formulas for the volume of financing (F) for a higher education institution and college at the expense of the state budget according to a new financing model containing the following components [20]:

$$F = F_1 + F_2 + F_3,$$

where F_1 is the volume (amount) of basic financing;

F_2 – volume (amount) of result-oriented financing;

F_3 – volume (amount) of targeted funding for innovation and development of teaching and research activities.

The volume (amount) of basic financing is calculated according to the formula:

$$F_1 = F_{1s} + F_{1z},$$

where F_{1s} is the volume (amount) of basic funding for teaching activities;

F_{1z} – volume (amount) of basic research funding.

The volume (amount) of result-oriented financing is calculated according to the formula:

$$F_2 = F_{2s} + F_{2z},$$

where F_{2s} is the volume (amount) of funding for teaching activities based on performance indicators;

F_{2z} – volume (amount) of research funding based on performance indicators.

The volume (amount) of financing innovations and development of teaching and research activities is calculated according to the formula:

$$F_3 = F_{3s} + F_{3z},$$

where F_{3s} – financing of capacity building for the development of innovative educational programs, creation of joint educational programs;

F_{3z} – support for strengthening the research and innovation potential of scientific institutions and the ability to attract external funding.

The amount of financing of the first component is determined in the order determined by the Cabinet of Ministers of Latvia, based on the number of study places determined by the institution of higher education, basic costs per study place, social security costs and coefficients of study costs in certain fields [20].

Financing of the second component of F_{2z} will be carried out at the expense of financial resources of the budget sub-program 03.03.00 Development of Scientific Activity in Institutions of Higher Education and Colleges.

Financial resources are allocated to the institution of higher education (Fatt) according to the new formulas provided for in the document Cabinet Regulation No. 994 [12]:

$$F_{2z} = F_{att} \left(\frac{\left(\frac{P}{\sum P} \right) + \left(\frac{S}{\sum S} \right) + \left(\frac{L}{\sum L} \right)}{3} \right),$$

where F_{2z} is the amount of financial resources allocated to a higher education institution;

F_{att} - financing under the subprogram 03.03.00 Development of Scientific Activity in Institutions of Higher Education and Colleges in the corresponding calendar year;

P is the number of masters and doctoral students who work as researchers in institutions of higher education, as well as researchers who have obtained a master's or doctorate degree in the last five years;

$\sum P$ is the total number of master's and doctoral students who work as researchers in higher education institutions, as well as researchers who have obtained a master's or doctoral degree in the last five years;

S - the amount of funding received within the framework of research projects implemented by a higher education institution within the framework of the European Union Framework Program and in other international competitions for research projects;

$\sum S$ – the total amount of funding involved in research projects implemented by a higher education institution within the framework of the European Union Framework Program (Framework Program of the European Union) and in other international competitions for research projects;

L – the amount of funding involved in the framework of research projects implemented in a higher education institution under an industry order, including contractual work with customers;

$\sum L$ is the total amount of funding raised within the framework of research projects implemented in a higher education institution under an industry order, including contractual work with customers.

The distribution of funding for each institution of higher education in Latvia is calculated according to the institution's contribution to each indicator. The Ministry of Education and Science (Ministry of Education and Science of Latvia) will determine the amount of funding depending on the relative performance indicators of the higher education institutions, comparing the total contribution of the institutions to the achievement of the educational policy goals. The sum of relative indicators is an indicator of the development of the research component in institutions of higher education [12].

The Law "On Institutions of Higher Education 1995" [1] (the Law "On Institutions of Higher Education") of 1995, as amended, regulates the legal basis of the activity of institutions of higher education in Latvia, establishes and protects their autonomy, regulates cooperation between institutions of higher education and state structures in order to reconcile the autonomy of higher education institutions with the interests of society and the state. In Art. 4 of this Law under the title "Autonomy of institutions of higher education" defines that "institutions of higher education are autonomous institutions in the field of education and science with the right of self-government. The autonomy of institutions of higher education involves the distribution of power and responsibility between state structures and the management of institutions of higher education, as well as between their management and academic staff [1].

The autonomy of the institution of higher education consists in the right to freely choose the types and forms of implementation of tasks, which are determined by the founders of the institution of higher education and correspond to this Law, as well as in the responsibility for [1]:

- the quality of the education received at the institution of higher education;
- expedient and rational use of financial and material resources;
- compliance with the principles of democracy, laws and other normative acts regulating the activities of higher education institutions."

According to Art. 4 Clause 3 of this Law, a Latvian institution of higher education has the right [1]:

- to develop and adopt the constitution of the institution of higher education;
- form the staff of the higher education institution;
- independently determine:
- content and forms of educational programs;
- additional rules for admission of persons, main directions of research work;
- organizational and management structure of the institution of higher education;

- wage rates are not lower than the rates established by the Cabinet of Ministers.

The founders determine the tasks of higher education institutions in accordance with Art. 5, in particular: "Institutions of higher education within their autonomy ensure the indivisibility of research work, the possibility of obtaining knowledge, academic education, professional skills, academic degrees and professional qualifications in the spheres of public life, national economy, culture, health care, public administration and other areas of professional activity. Institutions guarantee the academic freedom of staff and students by defining it in their constitutions" [1]. In 2009, amendments were made to the "Law On Institutions of Higher Education 1995" [1]. The consequence of these changes was a change in the legal status of higher education institutions in Latvia. In Art. 7 established: "institutions of higher education founded by the state (with the exception of the National Defense Academy of Latvia) are legal entities under public law (derived public persons)" [1]. In the document "State Administration Structure Law 2002" [21] (Law "On the structure of state administration") of 2002, as amended, it is defined that "a derived public person is a local self-government body or another state entity established in accordance to or under the law. Such a legal entity is granted autonomy, which also includes the preparation and approval of its own budget and the possibility of owning its own property" (Article 1).

That is, Latvian higher education institutions are not budgetary institutions, but institutions that receive funding from the budget. The consequence of the change in the legal status of institutions was the transition from the model of state control to the model of financial monitoring of institutions. According to Art. 80 of the Law "Law On Institutions of Higher Education 1995" [1], institutions of higher education in Latvia have the right to carry out the following types of economic activity [1]:

- to open branches, branches and representative offices;
- conclude contracts with individuals and legal entities, as well as perform other legal actions in accordance with this Law and other laws;
- announce tenders, buy and sell movable and immovable property, various property and securities in accordance with the current legislative acts and in accordance with the goals of the higher educational institution;
- carry out economic activity that corresponds to the institution's profile, the income from which is credited to the institution's budget for its development, as well as to invest the received funds in other enterprises in accordance with the goals of the institution of higher education.

Institutions of higher education that receive funds from the state budget must submit a written opinion prepared by an independent auditor on the results of economic activity, distribution and use of state budget funds, extrabudgetary revenues and their use to the Ministry of Education and Science of Latvia or to the ministry to which the relevant institution is subordinate.

Expenses in state institutions related to the inspection are covered by the state budget [1].

Regarding the financial resources of institutions of higher education, in Art. 77 "Law On Institutions of Higher Education 1995" [1] states that the founders finance institutions of higher education and exercise control over their use. The financial resources of state institutions of higher education include "funds of the state budget, as well as other income received by them for the implementation of activities for the realization of the goals defined by their constitutions. Institutions of higher education dispose of these revenues in compliance with the rules applicable to non-profit organizations [1]. Institutions of higher education in Latvia have the right to receive and use: donations and gifts from banks, other credit institutions, as well as organizations and individuals; loans from banks and other credit institutions [1]. The structure of financial resources of the institution of higher education is determined by the Senate. The rector submits an annual report on the implementation of the budget to the Senate, the Minister of Education and Science of Latvia or the founder of the higher education institution [1]. According to Art. 77 of the Law "On Institutions of Higher Education" [1], financial resources provided by individuals and legal entities to finance specific targeted programs and activities are transferred by the institution of higher education directly to the structural unit, individual or legal entity that implements this program or event. The financial resources of individual divisions of the institution of higher education as an independent part are included in the budget of the institution of higher education. If such a unit receives a donation (donation), the institution of higher education opens a special budget account (item 4, article 77) [1].

According to Clause 1 of Art. 76 Art. According to the Law "On Institutions of Higher Education" [1], the property of institutions of higher education can be land, movable, immovable property, intellectual property, as well as money in Latvia and foreign countries in accordance with the current legislative acts [1]. Institutions of higher education have the right to dispose of their property to achieve the goals specified in their constitutions. Property management is carried out separately from the state property transferred to them. In order to purchase real estate with budget funds allocated by the state, a higher education institution must obtain the consent of the Cabinet of Ministers (item 3, article 76) [1]. By decision of the Cabinet of Ministers, state-owned real estate may be transferred to the possession or disposal of state institutions of higher education (item 4, article 76) [1].

Institutions of higher education in Latvia can set tuition fees for students who are not studying at the expense of the State Budget on the basis of an agreement concluded between them (clause 2 of Article 52 "Law On Institutions of Higher Education 1995") [1]. Financial resources in the form of study fees are transferred to a special budget account of the institution of higher education and college and are used for the following purposes [1]:

- development of higher education institution and college;
- purchase of teaching aids and research equipment;
- purchase of equipment;
- financial stimulation of employees and students of higher education institutions and colleges, as well as remuneration of employees.

Institutions of higher education may set tuition fees for foreign students in accordance with the agreement concluded between them in an amount not less than the cost of education (clause 4 of Article 83 "Law On Institutions of Higher Education 1995") [1].

According to the European University Association, the level of financial autonomy of Latvian universities was 90%. Latvia is included in the "Top-cluster (High)" of countries in terms of the level of financial autonomy of universities (90%), which falls in the range from 81% to 100%. Despite the high importance of financial autonomy, in Latvia there are restrictions on the period of government funding of universities (one year), and the approval of the Cabinet of Ministers is required for transactions involving the acquisition of real estate objects.

Thus, at the national level, a three-dimensional model of financing higher education institutions has been introduced in Latvia, which includes the following components: "base funding" (basic funding of educational activities), "performance-based funding" (funding based on the results of the institutions' activities), "development funding" (financing the development of higher education and research). This model assumes that the financial resources of the State Budget are allocated to ensure stability and achieve strategic goals, and the resources of the Structural Funds of the European Union are aimed at creating the potential of higher education institutions. This enables Latvian higher education institutions to provide high-quality education that meets the needs of society and the development of the national economy of Latvia. As a result of reform processes in the field of higher education in Latvia, conditions have been created for the growth of university autonomy. In particular, institutions of higher education in Latvia have a high level of financial autonomy, which is guaranteed by legislative acts in the field of higher education. As a result of the change in the legal status of institutions of higher education in Latvia, autonomy was ensured regarding the preparation and approval of their own budgets and the possibility of owning their own property. Despite the high level, the financial autonomy of Latvian universities is limited by the term of state funding (one year) and restrictions on real estate transactions. Having analyzed the experience of financing higher education institutions of Latvia, we can speak with confidence about the possibility of using experience in the development of new ways of improving the financing of higher education institutions of Ukraine, in particular in the direction of attracting new sources of financing higher education.

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